

GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE IN UNIVERSITIES AND RESEARCH ORGANISATIONS

NATIONAL FIELDWORK REPORT

Country: Cyprus

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1. INTRODUCTION

Cyprus Universities and Research Organisations have not addressed the matter of Gender-Based Violence (hereinafter GBV) in a consistent manner in the last five years. Apart from two Universities that addressed GBV through encapsulating gender mainstreaming in the form of a Gender Equality Plan or Awareness Actions, including policies aiming to combat harassment and sexual harassment, there are no other publicly available policies specifically targeting GBV at Universities and Research Organisations. This demonstrates that Cyprus Universities and Research Organisations have yet to include GBV policies in their strategy and planning. Hence, a main implication derived from this research is the lack of prevalence studies on GBV at Universities and Research Organisations, which seems to affect general attitudes concerning the necessity for the existence of policies targeting GBV at Universities and Research Organisations.

2. MAPPING OF POLICIES AND LEGAL FRAMEWORKS

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To begin with, it is worth mentioning that Cyprus has ratified both the Optional Protocol to the United Nations Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW 1979) and the Council of Europe Convention on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence (Istanbul Convention 2014).

The Optional Protocol to the United Nations Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (Ratification) Law of 2002, L.1(III)/2002, does not explicitly include a definition for GBV. It does, however, impose a positive obligation on Cyprus to eliminate all forms of discrimination against women.

The Council of Europe Convention on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence (Ratification) Law of 2017, L.14(III)/2017, entered into force on the 28th July 2017. This Law ratified the Istanbul Convention by providing that it applies in Cyprus. This ratification law includes other laws in Cyprus that should be followed in conjunction, such as The Penal Code, the Criminal Procedure Law, the Equal Treatment of Men and Women in the Workplace Law and the Equal Pay Law. Furthermore, the Council of Ministers may issue Decrees for the implementation of this law. Law 14(III)/2017 includes the Istanbul Convention definition of “gender-based violence against women” and the definition of “violence against women”.

Apart from the above laws, no other legislation was identified to specifically target GBV at Universities and Research Organisations in Cyprus.

Concerning policies, Cyprus adopted the National Action Plan for the Equality of Men and Women 2019-2023 and the Strategic Plan for Equality between Men and Women 2018-2020. These two national action plans address GBV in general. The National Action Plan for Gender Equality mentions universities in some actions as taking part in research conducted to educate women to use computers and to create a platform for women to report incidents of violence. This mentioning, however, does not seek to address GBV in Universities and research organisations but rather uses universities to address gender equality in Cyprus and engage students and academics in gender mainstreaming. The other relevant Action Plan adopted for Education and developed by the Ministry of Education includes actions concerning harassment, bullying and violence, in high-level and general form. The focus is still on Gender Mainstreaming, and it includes GBV. The Action Plan specifically refers to encouraging Higher Education Institutions to create a Gender Plan concerning best practices and the promotion of equality, including the legal background, equal opportunities, fighting harassment and bullying.

The main actors and stakeholders that are responsible for the development of policies and strategies and their implementation in Cyprus are the Ministry of Education, Culture, Sport and Youth, the Cyprus Agency of Quality Assurance and Accreditation in Higher Education (CYQAA), the Ministry of Justice and Public Order, the Equality Commissioner, the Gender Equality in Employment and Vocational Training Committee and the Ministry of Labour, Welfare and Social Insurance, Department of Labour.

The lack of specific laws, policies and actions, to address GBV at Universities and Research Organisations in Cyprus demonstrates that more has to be done in order to be able to assess whether national and/or regional and RFO policies would have an impact on the organisational level of HEIs and RPOs in Cyprus. As the situation stands today, it is difficult to assess the impact of non-existent specific policies. It is worth mentioning, however, that some Universities decided to develop actions individually.

For instance, Frederick University launched the campaign "It starts with ME, together WE can" in 2019, in the framework of the international campaign 16 Days of Activism against Gender-Based Violence. This campaign is still active, but due to covid-19 restrictions, it is administered online.

Another relevant activity was launched by the state-owned Cyprus University of Technology (CUT). CUT decided to publish a Code of Conduct for Combatting Harassment and Sexual Harassment within the context of its Gender Equality Plan in 2021.

Apart from the above actions, there were partnerships between Non-Governmental Organisations and Universities conducting research on GBV. Some examples can be found on the website of the Mediterranean Institute of Gender Studies, Cyprus (MIGS 2021).

It is also worth mentioning that reported GBV, whether at Universities or not, is dealt with by the police as a crime, hence leading to the prosecution of the perpetrators in many instances.

In Cyprus, there is one official RFO, namely the Research and Innovation Foundation. At the moment, there are no specific incentives to universities or research organisations to address GBV. There are incentives to include gender mainstreaming in EU funded projects, and this includes addressing or having a policy for harassment and sexual harassment or at least a

response plan in case of an incident. There are also incentives by the Department of Labour for Equality Employers. These incentives do not specifically focus on GBV or at Universities and Research Organisations. As Employers, Universities and Research Organisations may choose to certify themselves as Equal Employers and adopt a Gender Equality Plan and a Code on Combatting Harassment and Sexual Harassment.

3. DEBATES REGARDING #METOO AND THE ISTANBUL CONVENTION

The Istanbul Convention was and is discussed in Cyprus in relevance to the ratification procedure as well as specific actions to combat violence against women. In 2017, the House of Parliament discussed the matter in detail and produced a report on the proceedings of the Convention ratification process. There was no specific reference to Universities and Research Organisations.

An organisation dedicated to preventing violence, the Association for the Prevention and Handling of Violence in the Family (SPAVO), published a positive statement about the ratification of the Istanbul Convention in 2017.

Another relevant public event on the ratification of the Istanbul Convention was organised by the University of Nicosia in 2017. The purpose of the event was the presentation of the ratification of the Istanbul Convention by Cyprus and two new Legislations promoting gender equality and combatting GBV in Cyprus. There were also some presentations by academics at the University of Nicosia concerning the Convention and the legal dimensions by the Minister of Justice, the Commissioner for Equality as well as SPAVO. The event was organised to promote action against GBV.

Finally, as mentioned above, Frederick University launched the campaign "It starts with ME, together WE can" in 2019, in the framework of the international campaign 16 Days of Activism against Gender-Based Violence. The aim of the campaign is to demonstrate the personal responsibility and power that each of us has to take the first step to end gender-based violence by challenging stereotypes and making small everyday behavioural changes that can lead to a large-scale shift of culture and attitudes in order to eliminate violence against women. This campaign is still active, but due to covid-19 restrictions, it is administered online.

4. PUBLIC OPINION ON GBV

No national public opinion surveys about GBV, specifically in universities and research organisations, were identified. There are, however, several studies and statistical reports concerning GBV in general.

Only one study concerning public opinion on GBV was identified. The study was conducted in 2012 by the Advisory Committee for the Prevention and Combating of Domestic Violence in the

Family, and it concerns domestic violence against women in Cyprus specifically. The results are interesting. However, they are now outdated since the study was conducted almost 10 years ago. The questions towards the public concerned their perceptions of family violence in Cyprus (what constitutes violence and what is the worst type of violence).

5. IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON DISCUSSIONS ABOUT GBV

COVID-19 has had a great impact on domestic violence cases in Cyprus. However, there was no publicly available discussion on the effect of COVID-19 on GBV at Universities or Research Organisations in Cyprus. It is possible that people who seek help through the designated helpline or the police are students and/or members of Universities' staff. However, this is not evident since there are no prevalence data.

6. CONCLUSION

Even though Cyprus is a small country, Universities and Research Organisations play a significant and growing role in the state economy. The number of students, both European and third-country nationals, stresses the importance of promoting prevalence studies to investigate and research the predominance of GBV at Universities. The state obligation to conduct prevalence studies and to address GBV is evident from the national Law ratifying the Istanbul Convention

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